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D3.3 3D Samples – Design & Manufacturing Report

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable provides information on design and manufacturing aspects of selected single innovative test channels. It summarizes the two confidential deliverables:

- D3.1 3D Samples – Structure Design Report
- D3.2 3D Samples – Manufacturing Conformity Report

Following previous confidential NATHENA deliverables, in particular the heat exchangers state of the art with its interpretation file, the database of existing concepts, the geometric concept report, the database of parametric optimisation and the “MS2: Simulation Review”, several structures were selected to be integrated in test channels. These test channels have been designed, additive layer manufactured and tested on a test bench.

The following pages describe the different test channels designs and their manufacturing. All geometries have been designed on CATIA V5 and RHINOCEROS 5, and all additive layer manufacturing have been performed on an ADDUP FORMUP 350 in aluminium AlSi7Mg and in Inconel 718. For general design information on single test channel geometries, please refer to “MS2: Simulation Review” confidential deliverable.

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3 SINGLE CHANNELS OVERVIEW

The test channels have been designed to take into account several aspects. The channels must:

- contain the different chosen patterns
- be interfaced with a test bench
- allow the fixation of test equipment
- be strong enough to ensure all previous characteristics
- be 3D printable

The picture below provide an overview with the overall dimensions of the test channel:

Figure 1: Test channel overall dimensions

The test channels allow an air passage section of 15 x 50mm. The tested patterns take place inside over a length of 100mm:

Figure 2: Test channel air passage section

The test channels must connect with a test bench. To achieve this, a specific interface has been designed at the entrance:

Figure 3: Test channel interface with test bench (1/2)

A groove is present to position a seal between the test channel and the test bench. The test channel is then fastened to the test bench thanks to a mechanical clamp and six screw/nut fasteners (in green):

Figure 4: Test channel interface with test bench (2/2)

In order to allow the fixation of test equipment, ten holes ($\varnothing$ 0.4mm) are located on the bottom side of the test bench. These hole allow temperature and pressure sensors to be placed along the tested patterns. The location can vary between two different test channels to avoid any collision between the sensors and the tested patterns:

Figure 5: Sensors locations

A heating resistor is placed on the upper side of the test channel. To ensure good contact, a plate screwed onto the channel presses on the resistor. Remote holes allow the use of a screw/nut system. In order to measure the temperature applied to the upper surface of the test channel by the heating resistor, five grooves are designed to allow the placement of thermocouples:

Figure 6: Thermocouples locations

Hereunder a picture of the heating resistor (in orange) pressed by the screwed plate (in blue). Four screw/nut fasteners ensure the compression force:

Figure 7: Heating resistor installation

The test channel must be vertically 3D printable to ensure a good printing behavior and minimize supports. To do so, the bottom of the seal groove is in the shape of a triangle and the remote holes for the press plate have an auto supporting structure:

Figure 8: Seal groove

Figure 9: Test channel auto supporting structure

4 INCONEL 718 SINGLE CHANNELS

4.1 CANAL_ESSAI_1_V1_I

4.1.1 Design

The Canal_Essai_1_V1_I channel uses a classic offset fin geometry, it has served to compare data to literature correlations, experimental and numerical studies, in order to fine tune the numerical model. Fins are 6.35mm in length, and they are spaced of 2mm between each other. Fins height matches the channel height. A 0.53mm space between each range has been added to avoid constrictions. The fin thickness has been set to 0.5mm in order to warranty good manufacturability.

Figure 10: Test channel design

4.1.2 Manufacturing

This channel has been printed with an inclination of 45° from the horizontal.

Figure 11: Printing orientation

Figure 12: Printed test channel

4.2 CANAL_ESSAI_1_V2_I

4.2.1 Design

Same design than Canal_Essai_1_V1_I.

4.2.2 Manufacturing

This channel has been printed with an inclination of 45° but with a second morphology of support. Oxidation has been limited as much as possible.

Figure 13: Printing orientation

Figure 14: Printed test channel

4.3 CANAL_ESSAI_2_V1_I

4.3.1 Design

This channel has been produced for roughness analysis with standard additive machine set-up. Thanks to this sample, it has been possible to account for surface roughness influence on part performance and its numerical model.

Canal_Essai_2_V1_I is in offset fins configuration. However, the shape of the fins is optimized to allow vertical manufacturing. The M shape consists in removing a triangle from the bottom edge on a classic rectangular fin. This modification is done to create a 45° angle between the surface and the printing direction. Thanks to this the spacing of 0,53mm between ranges can be removed. The fin length is equal to 15mm which is also the fin height. They are spaced of 2mm between each other. A thickness of 0.5mm is used to reduce risk of production failure.

Figure 15: Test channel design

4.3.2 Manufacturing

This channel has been printed vertically with a particular lasing strategy in order to avoid as much as possible wall roughness on fins. A base support has been added in order to make easier powder extraction after printing.

Figure 16: Printing orientation

Figure 17: Printed test channel

4.4 CANAL_ESSAI_3_V1_I

4.4.1 Design

Same design than Canal_Essai_2_V1_I.

4.4.2 Manufacturing

This channel has been printed vertically using a degraded contour strategy resulting in higher surface roughness. A base support has been added in order to make easier powder extraction after printing.

Figure 18: Printing orientation

Figure 19: Printed test channel

4.5 CANAL_ESSAI_3_V2_I

4.5.1 Design

Same design than Canal_Essai_2_V1_I.

4.5.2 Manufacturing

This channel has been printed vertically using a second degraded contour strategy resulting in higher surface roughness. A base support has been added in order to make easier powder extraction after printing.

Figure 20: Printing orientation

Figure 21: Printed test channel

4.6 CANAL_ESSAI_4_V1_I

4.6.1 Design

Canal_Essai_4_V1_I is used for low thickness wall test. The fin shape is here modified to have a thick leading edge followed by the thinnest manufacturable wall possible. The very thin wall is produced using a surface which warrants a single laser path. Thickness depends highly on the machine setup. This configuration grants the benefit of a high heat transfer on the leading edge whereas the low wall thickness behind reduces the weight of the fin and increases the developed surface. Height, length and fin spacing remain the same as previous geometry (Canal_Essai_2_V1_I) to be comparative.

Figure 22: Test channel design

4.6.2 Manufacturing

This channel has been printed vertically to avoid thermomechanical distortions. But the thin walls have been scratched during the layer making. The sample has been put off.

Figure 23: Printing orientation

Figure 24: Printed test channel

4.7 CANAL_ESSAI_5_V1_I

4.7.1 Design

Canal_Essai_5_V1_I channel uses the optimized X geometry tested in previous deliverable. This channel uses a lattice of X type initially set to fit an 8mm side cube and a 0.15mm radius struts. Those lattices have been deformed to reduce their frontal area and increase the developed surface. This structure has in consequence the best heat transfer to pressure drop ratio among the tested structures for a large range of Reynolds.

Figure 25: Test channel design

4.7.2 Manufacturing

This single test channel has been printed vertically to prevent thermomechanical distortions. Because of the fin's arrangement, a second support must be designed to help their printing. The support must be thought to be easily removable and strong enough to resist the mechanical efforts of layering.

Figure 26: Printing orientation

Figure 27: Printed test channel

4.8 CANAL_ESSAI_6_V1_I

4.8.1 Design

Gyroid were chosen for Canal_Essai_6_V1_I thanks to the new possibilities provided by the Additive Layer Manufacturing (ALM). The gyroid structure has an excellent manufacturability independently of the printing direction, thus, reducing manufacturing risk. Among the tested structures, gyroid structure shows a good fluidic and heat transfer performance with a very good flow mixing. This channel will allow to confirm the performance of this structure from both manufacturability and thermofluidic point of view. The gyroid unit cell size is π with a 4 times scale in fluid flow direction.

The gyroid complexity allows to overshoot classic design guidelines: the specific arrangement of the flow in gyroid allows to use the intensification structure as a separator between fluid flows, removing the need of plates and potentially reducing the weight.

Figure 28: Test channel design

4.8.2 Manufacturing

This single test channel has been printed vertically to avoid thermomechanical distortions.

Figure 29: Printing orientation

Figure 30: Printed test channel

4.9 CANAL_ESSAI_7_V1_I

4.9.1 Design

Canal_Essai_7_V1_I integrates evolutionary pattern of intensification structure. The aim is to have all along the test channel the best intensification structure regarding the local air flow characteristics: as the air in the channel advances, it heats up and its thermofluidic characteristics change. The intensification structures consist in 45° inclined and rectangular offset fins. 0.2mm thick and 1.5mm spacing at the inlet of the channel, and 0.6mm thick and 1.7mm spacing at the outlet. The channel height also varies: 4mm at the inlet and 8mm at the outlet. All geometric sizes vary linearly between the inlet and the outlet of the test channel. A 1mm space between each range has been added to avoid constrictions.

Figure 31: Test channel design

4.9.2 Manufacturing

Canal_Essai_7_V1_I has been printed in 45° direction using polyline support.

Figure 32: Printing orientation

Figure 33: Printed test channel

4.10 CANAL_ESSAI_8_V7_I

4.10.1 Design

The objective of Canal_Essai_8_V7_I integrate optimized intensification structures in the test channel based on fluid physical quantities such as temperature gradient, velocities and pressure gradient. These physical quantities are used to deform the structures shape. An initial 0.5mm diameter circular pin fin pattern with 2.5mm spacing was used, and iterations were done to progressively optimize it. As for the previous test channel, Canal_Essai_8_V7_I integrates evolutionary pattern of intensification structure all along the flow path.

Figure 34: Pin fin before (left) and after (right) iterations

Figure 35: Test channel design

4.10.2 Manufacturing

Canal_Essai_8_V7_I has been printed in 45° direction using a mix of polyline and massif support. The design of the intensification structures has not been rigid enough to support the top sample shape which explains the printing failure.

Figure 36: Printing orientation

Figure 37: Printed test channel

4.11 CANAL_ESSAI_9_V1_I

4.11.1 Design

Canal_Essai_9_V1_I integrates intensification structures that will be used for the hot side of the Inconel combined hot/cold test channel.

In order to select the best intensification structure in the future combined hot/cold test channel, a parametric optimisation study has been performed on several geometries to find the optimum shape and its geometric sizes. According to the deliverable “Database of parametric optimisation”, and “MS2: Simulation Review”, the selected hot fin shape is the offset chevron:

The chevron is 0.25mm thick, 4mm long and 4.5mm height. The offset spacing is 0.917mm.

Figure 38: Test channel design

4.11.2 Manufacturing

Canal_Essai_9_V1_I has been printed in vertical direction using a mixt of polyline and massif support.

Figure 39: Printing direction

Figure 40: Printed test channel

4.12 CANAL_ESSAI_10_V1_I

4.12.1 Design

Canal_Essai_10_V1_I integrates intensification structures that will be used for the cold side of the Inconel combined hot/cold test channel.

According to the deliverable “Database of parametric optimisation”, and “MS2: Simulation Review”, the selected cold fin shape is the offset chevron:

The chevron is 0.25mm thick, 1.75mm long and 7.65mm height. The offset spacing is 2.417mm.

Figure 41: Test channel design

4.12.2 Manufacturing

Canal_Essai_10_V1_I has been printed in vertical direction using a mix of polyline and massif support.

Figure 42: Printing direction

Figure 43: Printed test channel

5 ALUMINIUM ALSI7MG SINGLE CHANNELS

5.1 CANAL_ESSAI_1_V1_A

5.1.1 Design

Same design than Canal_Essai_1_V1_I.

5.1.2 Manufacturing

Same strategy than Canal_Essai_1_V1_I.

Figure 44: Printing orientation

5.2 CANAL_ESSAI_1_V2_A

5.2.1 Design

Same design than Canal_Essai_1_V1_I.

5.2.2 Manufacturing

Same strategy than Canal_Essai_1_V1_I.

Figure 45: Printing orientation

5.3 CANAL_ESSAI_2_V1_A

5.3.1 Design

Same design than Canal_Essai_2_V1_I.

5.3.2 Manufacturing

The test channel Canal_Essai_2_V1_A has not been printed since the roughness study on the test channel Canal_Essai_2_V1_I has been considered sufficient.

5.4 CANAL_ESSAI_3_V1_A

5.4.1 Design

Same design than Canal_Essai_2_V1_I.

5.4.2 Manufacturing

The test channel Canal_Essai_3_V1_A has not been printed since the roughness study on the test channel Canal_Essai_2_V1_I has been considered sufficient.

5.5 CANAL_ESSAI_4_V1_A

5.5.1 Design

Same design than Canal_Essai_4_V1_I but with 0.2mm thick fins instead of 0.15mm and leading edges with 1mm diameter.

Figure 46: Test channel design

5.5.2 Manufacturing

Canal_Essai_4_V1_A has been printed in vertical direction.

Figure 47: Printing orientation

5.6 CANAL_ESSAI_4_V2_A

5.6.1 Design

Same design than Canal_Essai_4_V1_I but leading edges with 1.2mm diameter.

Figure 48: Test channel design

5.6.2 Manufacturing

Canal_Essai_4_V2_A has been printed in vertical direction.

Figure 49: Printing orientation

5.7 CANAL_ESSAI_5_V1_A

5.7.1 Design

Same design than Canal_Essai_5_V1_I.

5.7.2 Manufacturing

Canal_Essai_5_V1_A has been printed in vertical direction.

Figure 50: Printing orientation

5.8 CANAL_ESSAI_6_V1_A

5.8.1 Design

Same design than Canal_Essai_6_V1_I.

5.8.2 Manufacturing

Canal_Essai_6_V1_A has been printed in vertical direction.

Figure 51: Printing orientation

5.9 CANAL_ESSAI_7_V1_A

5.9.1 Design

Canal_Essai_7_V1_A integrates evolutionary pattern of intensification structure. The aim is to have all along the test channel the best intensification structure regarding the local air flow characteristics: as the air in the channel advances, it heats up and its thermofluidic characteristics change.

The intensification structures consist in 45° inclined and rectangular offset fins. 0.29mm thick and 1.7mm spacing at the inlet of the channel, and 0.49mm thick and 1.55mm spacing at the outlet. The channel height also varies: 4mm at the inlet and 8mm at the outlet. All geometric sizes vary linearly between the inlet and the outlet of the test channel. A 1mm space between each range has been added to avoid constrictions.

Figure 52: Test channel design

5.9.2 Manufacturing

Canal_Essai_7_V1_A has been printed in 45° direction using polyline support.

Figure 53: Printing orientation

5.10 CANAL_ESSAI_8_V1_A

Following previous computational fluid dynamics (CFD) studies, it has been decided not to print this test channel.

5.11 CANAL_ESSAI_9_V1_A

5.11.1 Design

Canal_Essai_9_V1_A integrates intensification structures that will be used for the hot side of the Aluminium combined hot/cold test channel.

In order to select the best intensification structure in the future combined hot/cold test channel, a parametric optimisation study has been performed on several geometries to find the optimum shape and its geometric sizes. According to the deliverable “Database of parametric optimisation”, and “MS2: Simulation Review”, the selected hot fin shape is the offset chevron:

The chevron is 0.25mm thick, 6mm long and 7mm height. The offset spacing is 1.2mm.

Figure 54: Test channel design

5.11.2 Manufacturing

Canal_Essai_9_V1_A has been printed in vertical direction using a mixt of polyline and massif support.

Figure 55: Printing orientation

Figure 56: Printed test channel

5.12 CANAL_ESSAI_10_V1_A

5.12.1 Design

Canal_Essai_10_V1_A integrates intensification structures that will be used for the cold side of the Aluminium combined hot/cold test channel.

According to the deliverable “Database of parametric optimisation”, and “MS2: Simulation Review”, the selected cold fin shape is the offset chevron:

The chevron is 0.25mm thick, 4.35mm long and 8mm height. The offset spacing is 2.75mm.

Figure 57: Test channel design

5.12.2 Manufacturing

Canal_Essai_10_V1_A has been printed in vertical direction using a mixt of polyline and massif support.

Figure 58: Printing orientation

Figure 59: Printed test channel

6 SYNTHESIS

The following table summarizes which test channel has been printed and which test channel has been instrumented. For test campaign, please refer to confidential deliverables “Test Specifications” and “Single Channel Tests, Results and Analyses”.

Test Channel Reference	Printed	Instrumented
Canal_Essai_1_V1_I	YES	YES
Canal_Essai_1_V2_I	YES	YES
Canal_Essai_2_V1_I	YES	YES
Canal_Essai_3_V1_I	YES	YES
Canal_Essai_3_V2_I	YES	PENDING
Canal_Essai_4_V1_I	YES but unusable	-
Canal_Essai_5_V1_I	YES	YES
Canal_Essai_6_V1_I	YES	YES
Canal_Essai_7_V1_I	YES	YES
Canal_Essai_8_V7_I	YES but unusable	-
Canal_Essai_9_V1_I	YES	YES
Canal_Essai_10_V1_I	YES	PENDING
Canal_Essai_1_V1_A	YES	YES
Canal_Essai_1_V2_A	YES	PENDING
Canal_Essai_2_V1_A	NO (useless)	-
Canal_Essai_3_V1_A	NO (useless)	-
Canal_Essai_4_V1_A	YES	YES
Canal_Essai_4_V2_A	YES	YES
Canal_Essai_5_V1_A	YES	YES
Canal_Essai_6_V1_A	YES	YES
Canal_Essai_7_V1_A	YES	YES
Canal_Essai_8_V1_A	NO (useless)	-
Canal_Essai_9_V1_A	YES	PENDING
Canal_Essai_10_V1_A	YES	PENDING